

Content Analysis of Mathematics Textbooks and Adapted Lorenz Curves

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In this paper, we introduce an adaptation of the Lorenz curve as a powerful tool for graphically presenting content analyses of mathematics textbooks. Three textbooks currently used with year-one children in Sweden, one Swedish-, one Finnish and one Singaporean-authored, were analysed against the eight categories of Foundational Number Sense (FoNS), which is a set of literature-derived and instruction-dependent competences that all children need to acquire if they are to become successful learners of mathematics. The adapted Lorenz curve highlighted, inter alia, major differences in the distribution of FoNS-related tasks across the three textbooks. In general, the Swedish-authored textbook offers repeated cycles of FoNS-related opportunities, the Finnish-authored textbook offers such opportunities continuously, and the Singaporean-authored textbook typically offers FoNS-related opportunities only within its earlier pages.

Introduction

Two years ago, at MEI7, we introduced moving averages as a tool for presenting textbook content analyses (Petersson et al., 2019). This paper extends that work by offering a second approach, which we label adapted Lorenz curves, which also shows in graphically transparent and reader-friendly ways how textbooks emphasise and distribute content.

Why Analyse Textbooks?

There are at least three reasons for analysing mathematics textbooks. First, particularly in cultures in which textbook production is effectively deregulated, it is important to evaluate a textbook's content against curricular specifications. In such circumstances, where textbooks are intended to make the curriculum visible (Park & Leung, 2006; Son & Senk, 2010), teachers should have confidence that they address adequately the system's expected outcomes. Importantly, dependent on national context, the textbook is afforded different responsibilities with respect to what children are expected to learn, with differing consequences for the teachers who use them. On the one hand, for example, are systems like Cyprus, where teachers are mandated to use the government-produced textbooks that, de facto, represent the intended curriculum (Travers & Weinzveig, 1999). Here, there is, in essence, no need for teachers to evaluate textbooks' curricular resonance because there are no permitted alternatives (Xenofontos, 2019). On the other hand, in a system like Ireland, where few teachers do not use textbooks as the basis for their teaching (Mullis et al., 2012) and publishers operate in a deregulated market, the responsibility for any evaluation of their resonance with the state-mandated learning outcomes lies with the teacher. Put another way, in Ireland, due to individual authors' interpretation of curricular expectations, textbooks there form part of the implemented curriculum (Travers & Weinzveig, 1999).

The second reason, also of particular relevance to Ireland, is that even if two textbooks are similarly adequate in their addressing of curricular expectations, they may do so in

different ways. Topics and the subtopics within them may be sequenced differently or topics may be given different emphases. Generic competences like problem solving may be privileged more in some books than in others, with some offering such tasks in a continuous chain of opportunity and others locating them at the different chapters' ends. In other words, in systems in which teachers have multiple choices with regard to the textbooks they use, comparing textbooks' approaches to mathematics is important. For example, Neuman et al. (2014) found substantial variation in the support for teachers in textbooks written for use in Swedish primary schools. Thus, while this may not be the case for teachers in countries like South Korea, where textbook reviews occur centrally at ministry level (Son & Senk, 2010), teachers in systems like Ireland and Sweden are, de facto, expected to be able to undertake such reviews themselves.

The third reason concerns the importation of textbooks from one country to another. Over the last few years, publishers, particularly in countries with unregulated textbook markets, have imported textbooks from countries whose students have excelled on large-scale tests of achievement. For example, Singaporean textbook series have been adapted for use in England and Sweden (Petersson et al., 2019), the Netherlands (van Zanten & van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, 2018) and the United States (Hoven & Garelick, 2007). While the publishers of such imports typically claim that their books have been adapted to local curricular expectations, it is important for to acknowledge that teaching and learning are deeply culturally situated (Merttens, 2015).

In sum, while all three reasons invoke, in different ways, notions of curriculum matching, they also allude to three different but important perspectives governing how textbooks are produced and used (Rezat and Strässer, 2015). The first is the author perspective, which acknowledges both the addressed curriculum and individual authors' preferences. The second is the user perspective, which refers to how mathematics books are used by students and teachers and reflects, in varying degrees, what Johansson (2006) has described as room for manoeuvre. The third is the content perspective, which deals with, essentially, the didactical aspects of a book's content, including its distribution, presentational variation, and levels of difficulty. In this paper, acknowledging such matters, we offer an analytical tool hitherto unknown in research on school mathematics textbooks, which we believe facilitates all forms of textbook analysis and comparison in powerfully visual ways. By way of demonstration, we draw on three textbooks currently used with year-one children in Sweden. While each book has its roots in a different curriculum tradition, each, according to its publisher, has been adapted to address the Swedish national curriculum. These are *Matte Eldorado*, a Swedish-authored series, *Favorit*, an adapted Finnish-authored series, and *Singma*, an adapted Singaporean-authored series.

Methods

Analytical Framework

As with our earlier paper (Petersson et al., 2019), analyses drew on the eight categories of Foundational Number Sense, hereafter FoNS, which is a set of literature-derived

and instruction-dependent competences that all children need to acquire if they are to become successful learners of mathematics (Andrews & Sayers, 2015). For each book, all tasks that expected some form of action on the part of the student were examined by at least two members of the project team. Each task addressing one of the FoNS categories, shown in Table 1, was coded ‘1’ for that opportunity and ‘0’ otherwise. In this manner, every task in each book attracted eight codes, according to the presence or absence of the eight FoNS categories. In this way, many tasks, particularly geometrical, attracted no codes, while many attracted several. For example, Figure 1 shows a task inviting children to “compare the number of dots” and then “write either = or \neq ” in the box. This task occurred before the book introduced addition, and was viewed as encouraging solution by counting and coded for *systematic counting*. Expectations of equality or inequality led to its being coded for *quantity discrimination*, the dot patterns not only alluded to *different representations of number*, but also hinted at subitising and an *awareness of the relationship between number and quantity*. In other words, this task attracted four codes of ‘1’ (codes 2–5 in table 1) and four of ‘0’.

Figure 1

A multiply coded textbook example

Table 1

Summary of the eight categories of foundational number sense

FoNS Category	Teachers encourage children, within the range 0-20, to
1. Number recognition	Identify, name and write particular number symbols
2. Systematic counting	Count systematically, forwards and backwards, from arbitrary starting points
3. Number and quantity	Understand the one-to-one correspondence between number and quantity
4. Quantity discrimination	Compare magnitudes and deploy language like ‘bigger than’ or ‘smaller than’
5. Different representations	Recognise and make connections between different representations of number
6. Estimation	Estimate the magnitude of a set of objects or place a given number on empty number line
7. Simple arithmetic	Perform simple addition and subtraction operations
8. Number patterns	Recognise and extend number patterns, identify a missing number

Analytical Tool: The Adapted Lorenz Curve

The process outlined above means that all the tasks in each book collectively create a sequence of ones and zeros where each ‘1’ affirms that the task addresses a particular FoNS category. In this way, premised on all tasks in a book forming a time-delimited series of activities, different forms of analyses can be undertaken. In particular, an adapted Lorenz curve is simply a plot of the cumulative sum of the number of occurrences of a FoNS category. This means, for example, that if the first six tasks in a book were coded 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1... for, say, FoNS1, its cumulative sum becomes 0, 1, 2, 2, 2, 3..., a sequence amenable to a graphing process similar to that of a cumulative frequency curve. Indeed, as we show below, an adapted Lorenz curve shows how particular content, say FoNS 1, is distributed throughout the textbook. Of course, such a process does not account for teachers exploiting possible room for manoeuvre (Johansson, 2006) through choosing to alter the order in which they teach, or even omit, the material (Mesa, 2004), but it does offer a clear indication of the authors’ intentions, emphases and timing.

Results

Figure 2

Adapted Lorenz curve for Eldorado

Figures 2-4 show the adapted Lorenz curves for each of the eight FoNS categories for each book respectively. It can be seen clearly that each time a task is coded for the presence of a FoNS category, the adapted Lorenz curve rises and when that category is missing, it contributes a horizontal component. While several similarities and differences can be inferred from the three figures, we turn first to the former. The most obvious similarity is that all three books place the greatest emphasis on FoNS1 and FoNS7 (number recognition and simple arithmetical operations respectively). Moreover, the vertical differences between the two graphs, indicate that FoNS7 develops at slower pace than FoNS1. Elsewhere, in each figure, they are effectively parallel, meaning that they tend either to occur simultaneously or not at

all. The second is that all three books emphasis FoNS3 and FoNS5 (Awareness of the relationship between number and quantity, and awareness of different representations of number respectively), although this is stronger in Eldorado than either Favorit or Singma. Across the three figures, the graphs for FoNS3 and FoNS5 are essentially parallel, with the consequence that they occur either simultaneously or not at all. The third is that the remaining FoNS categories either receive low emphases or, as with FoNS6 (estimation) are essentially absent. Before discussing their differences, we now turn to the characteristics of each book.

With respect to Eldorado, it can be seen in Figure 2 that the majority of the different FoNS curves show a repeated pattern of periods of growth, indicative of tasks repeatedly addressing the category under scrutiny, followed by periods of constancy, indicating no tasks addressing the category under scrutiny. This pattern is especially evident in the tasks found in the second half of the book, highlighting, it seems to us, two important features. The first is that these patterns, which tend to occur simultaneously, are distinguished only by the differences in the gradients of the growth periods. In other words, Eldorado seems to address several FoNS categories at the same time. The second is a corollary of the first, namely, the periods of constancy, represented by the horizontal lines, emphasise sections in the book where topics other than number are presented.

Figure 3

Adapted Lorenz curve for Favorit (the scale follows the number of tasks)

From the perspective of Favorit, the curve for each FoNS category shown in Figure 3 (except FoNS6) has hardly any plateaus. There are hints, around the middle of the book, of limited FoNS-related activity, but, overall, the graphs show that number-related opportunities are a constant presence. The only exceptions are FoNS6 (estimation) and FoNS8 (number patterns). The former is, de facto, absent and the latter, introduced in a very limited manner towards the end of the book. The different Singma graphs shown in Figure 4, present a very different story. With a single exception, no tasks were found to address any FoNS category

after the first 40% of the books' tasks. In fact, our analyses found that later number-related tasks fell outside the FoNS categorisations, involving only numbers in the range 21-100. The solitary exception is FoNS2 (systematic counting), which is clearly subject to a second period of emphasis around three-quarters of the way through the book.

Figure 4

Adapted Lorenz curve for Singma

From the perspective of differences, the graphs shown in each figure highlight well very different didactical representations of the different FoNS categories. For example, irrespective of the FoNS category under scrutiny, the graphs for Swedish-authored Eldorado show a repeated pattern, whereby a category is present for a period followed by its being absent for a period. By way of contrast, and acknowledging the effective absence of two FoNS categories, when Finnish-authored Favorit addresses a FoNS category it does so continuously throughout the book. Finally, Singapore-authored Singma, with a single exception in FoNS2 and two FoNS categories absent, essentially offers continuous opportunities for children to engage with five FoNS categories during the early part of the book, after which FoNS disappears from a child's experience as more complex material is introduced.

Discussion

In an era in which textbooks written in countries deemed successful on international tests of achievement are imported into other countries, typically on the untested assumption that they must be of a higher quality than those produced by the importing countries, it is important for researchers to have efficient tools for evaluating the efficacy and, for teachers, the adaptability, of such imports. In this paper, we have analysed three textbooks currently used with year-one children in Sweden. One, Eldorado, is Swedish-authored, while the others, Favorit and Singma, are Finnish- and Singaporean authored respectively. Analyses were

structured by the eight categories of Foundational Number Sense, a core set of literature-derived and instruction-dependent competences that all children need to acquire if they are to become successful learners of mathematics (Andrews & Sayers, 2015). In undertaking these analyses, we have extended an earlier study in which we introduced moving averages as a novel tool for analysing the content of school mathematics textbooks (Petersson et al., 2021), by introducing adapted Lorenz curves, to further extend an important and necessary toolkit. As we have shown, the adapted Lorenz curves have highlighted well how textbooks' authors emphasise and distribute different forms of mathematical knowledge.

The analyses identified important differences and similarities, confirming, we argue, the relevance and efficacy of the adapted Lorenz curve. The most obvious similarity was that all three books emphasised the same four FoNS categories concerning; number recognition; simple arithmetical operations; awareness of the relationship between number and quantity; and awareness of different representations of number respectively. A second was that all three books offered few opportunities for children to engage with the remaining four FoNS categories. A major difference, well exemplified by the adapted Lorenz curves, concerned the distribution of FoNS-related tasks across the three textbooks and the didactical implications inferred from them. In general, Swedish-authored Eldorado appears to present repeated cycles of opportunity for children to engage with the different FoNS categories of competence. Finnish-authored Favorit offers such opportunities continuously throughout the school year and Singaporean-authored Singma offers FoNS-related learning, with a single exception, only within its earlier pages. In other words, if a textbook's role is to make visible a system's curricular expectations (Park & Leung, 2006; Son & Senk, 2010; Travers & Weinzeig, 1999), then these three commonly-used textbooks not only present very different images of the Swedish curriculum but also require teachers to manage intelligently the room for manoeuvre they offer (Johansson, 2006).

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